

RANDOM DISTURBING MODEL FOR THERMAL EXPANSION PROPERTY PREDICTION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

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1 General Introduction

The composite materials are widely used in aeronautics and astronautics because of their outstanding mechanical-thermal performance. Unidirectional (UD) fiber reinforced composite is one of the most important materials in aeronautic and astronautic applications. As technology advances, the demands of rigorous dimension stability of material and structure are put forward for high-precision apparatus in aerocrafts. So it is absolutely crucial that known of the basic properties of material, especially the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in designing structures with high dimensional stability.

Recently, scholars have done lots of work on the CTE performance of unidirectional fiber reinforced composite [1-8]; most of the work are theoretical analysis of CTE by use of thermo-elastic mechanics or energy principles, including the work done by Van Fo Fy, Schapery and Rosen&Hashin etc; they derived explicit expressions of CTEs of composite by studying the properties of its constituents. Such methods facilitate the application, and can predict longitudinal CTEs very well; however, there exist rather large differences between the predicted transverse CTE and tested CTE of composite, the errors can be as high as 50%. Whereas, it's crucial that precisely predicting the CTEs of composite to design structures with high dimensional stability.

When Finite Element Method (FEM) developed, Z.Haktan [6] adopted numerical methods to study the representative volume element (RVE) of composite to predict its CTEs. However, those RVEs are always simplified to be a single fiber together with surrounded matrix, thus such models can't reflect the real arrangement of fiber in composite, nor can reflect the influence of CTEs by fiber arrangement. As always, fiber arrangement is

considered to be an important factor that dominates interior stress that caused by temperature changes. Stress distribution would have a remarkable effect on the mechanical and thermal performance of composite.

In order to explain the influence on CTEs of composite by fiber arrangement, models with near real arrangement should be considered. Chen Xiaoming etc. [7-11] created models by sequentially disturbing fibers that uniformly distributed in advance in random directions, thus can get models with randomly distributed fibers. Such models can be used to predict mechanical thermal properties of composites. But those models didn't take the fibers that are cut by boundaries into account.

Another technique to generate randomly distributed fiber is hard-core method [12], but such a method can hardly generate models with fiber content more than 50%. Random sequential adsorption method [13] developed quickly in recent years and it can generate randomly distributed fiber by adsorbing fibers to a previous one and fiber content in such models can be as high as 54.7%, but still not enough for engineering use. A.R Melro[14] improved an algorithm based on hard-core method, and can make fiber content more than 60%, however, such an algorithm is somewhat complicated.

This paper developed a fiber random distribution method based on Chen[7-11]. This algorithm should be able to deal with high fiber content model and be as simple as possible.

Finally, models with unidirectional fibers generated by such an algorithm, together with periodic boundary conditions, were used to predict the CTEs of composite T300/5208, P75/930, P75/934, P75/CE339 and E-glass/epoxy. Comparisons were made between predicted results and experimental

data; compared results showed that predicted results well-matched experimental data.

2 FEM Modeling

2.1 Randomly packing of fiber

Composites to be studied in this paper are all unidirectional fiber reinforced composites, and the fibers in the cross-plane that perpendicular to the fiber are assumed to be randomly distributed. This assumption is rational according to lots of micro-graphic studies by other scholars.

In order to ensure the fiber content of composite model can be large enough for practical usage, and keep the random distribution character of fiber in the transverse section of unidirectional fiber reinforced composite. A modified Random Disturbing Method (RDM) is put forward, which is based upon methods by Hai [10], Chen [11] and Wongsto [15]. RDM works as follow:

(1) Input model dimension parameters (v_f, r_f, k) , so as to create the initial model which fibers distribute hexagonally uniformly. Where v_f stands for the target fiber content; r_f is the radius of fiber; k controls the basic dimension of model and the number of fiber N_f . The initial model sees in Fig.1 (a).

Fig.1 Initial model and disturbing principle

(2) Generate a random number i_f . Where i_f stands for the selected fiber for i th disturbing process, and each fiber can only be selected once during all the disturbing processes.

(3) Generate random numbers θ_i and $disp_i$ that attribute to a certain Poisson distribution. θ_i represents the disturbing direction relative to the fiber's current position, and it should be within

$0 - 2\pi$. $disp_i$ is the disturbing displacement, and it can range from 0 to $dist_f$.

$$dist_f = 2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{12}v_f}} - 1 \right) r_f \quad (1)$$

(4) Disturb randomly selected fiber i_f with parameters θ_i and $disp_i$, and auto count the disturbing times (*count*) for current fiber i_f . Disturbing process sees in Fig.1 (b).

(5) Determine whether fiber i_f the one on the boundary of RVE. If so, the fiber i_f must have been cut by boundary, the counterpart of fiber i_f that is i'_f should be disturbed with the same parameters as fiber i_f . this step is mainly to ensure the periodic boundary conditions and of composite.

(6) Verify the distance between the fibers that have been disturbed and anyone else to make sure no fiber would overlap another. According to the studies by Trias D[19], the distance between any two fiber centers should be no less than $(2 + 0.05) \times r_f$. For the fibers on the boundary, make sure that they would not beyond the bound of RVE.

(7) If current disturbed fibers overlapped any other fiber, then return to step (3), regenerate θ_i and $disp_i$, disturb the selected fiber again until the least distance rules are satisfied or the disturbing times *count* exceeds a previous given disturbing time limit (*count_limit*).

(8) If *count* exceeds *count_limit*, then return to step (2), redo the steps above again until all fibers are successfully disturbed.

The flow chart of RDM shows in Fig.2. Such an algorithm can deal with RVEs with fiber content as high as 90%. The key point in this RDM algorithm is disturbing randomly selected fiber in random direction by random distance; no fiber overlaps, no fiber outturns the boundary of RVE.

Fig. 2 Randomly disturbing process

2.2 Periodic boundary

RVE represents a part of continuous material, which means that the unidirectional fiber reinforced composite can be considered as a collectivity of numerous such of RVEs, so the boundaries shared by neighboring RVE should have the same displacement vector while stresses in opposite direction [16-17]. So, periodic boundary conditions should be applied on the RVE to ensure the continuous displacement, stress and strain field. The periodic boundary conditions are as follows [17]:

$$u_i(l, y, z) = u_i(0, y, z) + \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} l \quad i = x, y, z \quad (2)$$

$$u_i(x, w, z) = u_i(x, 0, z) + \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} w \quad i = x, y, z \quad (3)$$

$$u_i(x, y, h) = u_i(x, y, 0) + \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} h \quad i = x, y, z \quad (4)$$

In the above equations, u is displacement function; l, w and h stand for the dimensions of the RVE in $x,$

y and z direction respectively. To explain the equations above, a simplified 2D model shows in Fig.3, where L, R, T and B stand for the left, right, top and bottom boundary, they are grouped into two pair boundaries (L and R, T and B). The equations (2-4) then can be simplified as follows:

$$u_R - u_{RB} = u_L - u_{LB} \quad (5)$$

$$u_T - u_{LT} = u_B - u_{LB} \quad (6)$$

$$u_{RT} - u_{LT} - u_{RB} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Where u_i denotes the displacement vector of boundary i ; u_{ij} is the displacement vector of corner point intersected by boundary i and j . other displacement conditions are shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 Periodic boundary principle of RVE

2.3 Software and model

For predicting properties of unidirectional fiber reinforced composite by fiber random packing model, one of the questions is what number of model would be large enough to satisfy statistics requirements. In this research, there are 5 models for each given parameter such as fiber content. Another problem is what size of the RVE will be ok; too small a model is hardly able to represent the characters of fiber random distributions; too large a model is hard to deal with, especially by numerical method, because the computation time increases by power of 3, which means if the dimensions of RVE doubled, the computation time will be 8 times as that before. According to the research done by Trias D[17], the critical dimension of RVE that satisfied statistic requirements is $50 \times r_f$. The cross-section dimensions of the models created by RDM are all set to be almost 50 times of the fiber's radius; while the axial dimension is no need to obey this rule, because

the property of UD composite in axial direction are assumed to be constant.

Fig.4 Random disturbing model

Software package Matlab R2009 and MSC Patran 2010 were used to generate those random disturbing models, and Nastran 2010 was adopted to do the numerical analysis. One of the generated random disturbing finite element models is as in Figure.4. Blue cylinders stand for reinforcement (fiber), semi-cylinders in two boundary pairs are counterparts of each other; also, the 4 quart-cylinders can be assembled into a full cylinder that stands for a fiber.

Table.2 Properties of fibers at room temperature [5,18]

Fiber	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	u_{12}	u_{12}	1.0E-6/ °C	
							α_1	α_2
T300	233.13	23.11	8.97	8.28	0.20	0.40	-0.54	10.08
C6000	233.13	23.11	8.97	8.28	0.20	0.40	-0.54	10.08
P75	550.40	9.52	6.90	3.38	0.20	0.40	-1.35	6.84
Glass fiber	72.00	72.00	30.00	30.00	0.20	0.20	5.00	5.00

3 Results and Conclusion

From the properties of constituents that are listed in Table 1 and Table 2, it can be found that the unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite material systems have an axial fiber to matrix stiffness ratio (E_{f1}/E_m) ranging from 20 to 126 and axial fiber to

The properties of constituents used for numerical analysis are listed in table 1-2. The data about Epoxy and Glass fiber are extracted from research by Sideridis [5], other data are taken from Bowles and Tompkins [18], they assumed 934,930,5208 and CE339 epoxy have the same properties except CE339 has a relative larger CTE. Also, fiber T300 and C6000 are assumed all the properties the same. All fibers are transverse isotropic while matrix are isotropic in all directions.

Coefficients of thermal expansion will be calculated by equation (8)

$$a = \frac{\Delta l}{l \Delta T} \quad (8)$$

CTEs in x, y and z directions of each model can be derived from equation (8). As there are 5 models for each given fiber content parameter, so the final results are the average values in transverse and longitudinal directions.

Table.1 Properties of matrix at room temperature [5,18]

Matrix	E (GPa)	G (GPa)	u	α (1.0E-6/ °C)
934 epoxy	4.35	1.59	0.37	43.92
930 epoxy	4.35	1.59	0.37	43.92
5208 epoxy	4.35	1.59	0.37	43.92
Epoxy	3.50	1.41	0.35	52.50
CE339 epoxy	4.35	1.59	0.37	63.36
PMR15polyimide	3.45	1.31	0.35	36.00

matrix coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) ratio (a_{f1}/a_m) ranging from -0.012 to 0.096. As a result, this investigation covers a wide range of fiber/matrix combinations.

Based on the models created by RDM algorithm, CTEs of UD composites with different fiber content are predicted. The fiber content ranges from 10% to

80% by 10%, there are 5 models in each fiber content group for the statistic consideration, and the average CTE in each group models is taken as the final result of CTE.

Comparisons are carried out among CTEs predicted by RDM, experiments, and some analytical solutions, including modified Schapery's equation [6], Chamberlain's and Scheider's equations; the comparisons are carried out at different fiber volume fractions from 10% to 80% as can be seen in Fig.5-14. There are six different fiber and matrix systems in this paper to verify this RDM; they are P75/930, P75/934, P75/CE339, T300/5208, C6000/PMR15 polyimide and E-glass/epoxy. Fig.5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 are the transverse CTE comparisons of those material systems while Fig.6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 are the longitudinal CTE comparisons. The data for P75/930 and P75/934 are put in one figure for each direction, because the two composites are the same material system.

Figure 5, 7, 9 are transverse CTE comparisons for material system T300/5208, C6000/Pi and E-glass/epoxy. The close distance between experimental data and RDM represents good agreement with predictions by RDM. The longitudinal CTEs predicted by RDM and Schapery that showed in Fig.6, 8 and 10 are nearly the same, and predictions match test data well.

Figure 11-12 is the comparisons of predicted CTEs of P75/930 and P75/934 by different methods. Compared to CTEs predicted by RDM, Schapery's methods are in less difference than the other two methods. It can be seen that the experimental datum of P75/934 is closer to RDM while P75/930 is closer to Schapery's prediction. However, the longitudinal CTE predictions by RDM and Schapery are almost the same, and predictions are in good accord with tested data. Same response can be found for P75/CE339 in Fig.13 and Fig.14.

Although the predicted results showed some differences among them, the trend was the same. That is as the fiber content increases, predicted CTEs decreases. The transverse CTE descends almost linearly, while the longitudinal CTE descends rapidly at first and until fiber content exceeds 60%.

Fig.5 Transverse CTE for T300/5208

Fig.6 Longitudinal CTE for T300/5208

Fig.7 Transverse CTE for C6000/Pi

Fig.8 Longitudinal CTE for C6000/Pi

Fig.11 Transverse CTE for P75/930 and P75/934

Fig.9 Transverse CTE for E-glass/epoxy

Fig.12 Longitudinal CTE for P75/930 and P75/934

Fig.10 Longitudinal CTE for E-glass/epoxy

Fig.13 Transverse CTE for P75/CE339

Fig.14 Longitudinal CTE for P75/CE339

Despite errors exist, the general response behaves the same (decreasing longitudinal CTE with increasing fiber content), which indicates that the relative magnitudes of the fiber/matrix stiffness and CTE ratios do not significantly affect the general trend in longitudinal CTE. Furthermore, we can find that for a same material system, such as T300/5208 and C6000-pi, the larger CTE the matrix have, the more dramatic the CTE of composite decrease until fiber content exceeds 60%. For a same matrix, the larger the modulus and absolute value of axial CTE the fiber have, the more dramatically the longitudinal CTE of such a material combination decreases (e.g. P75/934).

Fig.6, 8, 10, 12, 14 are the longitudinal CTE response as fiber content increases. It can be concluded that the axial CTE of UD composite is dominated by the reinforcement, such as fiber. Usually, the fiber to matrix stiffness ratio (E_{f1}/E_m) is much greater than 1.0 and CTE ratio (a_{f1}/a_m) smaller than 1.0; so, as fiber content increases, the axial CTE decrease rapidly at first and when fiber content is more than 70%, the axial CTE of composite will get close to that value of fiber.

Fig.5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 show the response of transverse CTE as a function of fiber volume fraction for different material combinations. Experimental data and FEM results are also shown in figures mentioned above. The maximum error between RDM and experimental results is $5.671E-6/^\circ\text{C}$, while the maximum error between Schapery and experimental results is $6.696E-6/^\circ\text{C}$.

As can be seen in Fig.5, 7, 9, 11 and 13, unlike the axial CTE, the response of transverse CTE as a

function of fiber volume fraction is affected by both the fiber to matrix stiffness ratio (E_{f2}/E_m) and transverse CTE ratio (a_{f2}/a_m). P75/930 has a similar fiber to matrix stiffness ratio ($E_{f2}/E_m < 1$) with P75/CE339, so the response of transverse CTE decreases with increasing fiber volume fraction. However, P75/CE339 has larger transverse CTE ratio ($a_m/a_{f2} > 1$), so the transverse CTE of P75/CE339 drops more steeply than P75/930.

3 References

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